

Template and Guidelines for Developing Survey Protocols

Creating monitoring standards compatible with the Ecological Monitoring System of Australia

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Acknowledgements and contributors

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Version control

The version history of this document is identified below. Enquiries regarding version control should be directed to tern@adelaide.edu.au

Version	Date	Version update overview
1	21 November 2025	Version 1 publication
2	19 February 2026	Version 2 publication – minor fixes to broken weblinks

About

This document, a *Template and Guidelines for Developing Survey Protocols: Creating monitoring standards compatible with the Ecological Monitoring System Australia (EMSA)*, guides users to develop standardised field survey protocols.

EMSA has been developed by TERN (the Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network), in collaboration with the Australian Government Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water (DCCEEW). The protocols included in EMSA build on previous work by numerous ecologists throughout the country, and have been refined with the help of Australia's natural resource management (NRM) community. As EMSA now commences an important phase of extending its use, including to inform impact assessment, it is essential to transfer the knowledge and experience developed by TERN to others.

The EMSA modules provide users with a clear set of proven protocols (built on previous methods where appropriate) for measuring and monitoring the majority of Australian terrestrial ecosystems in a quantitative, repeatable manner, enabling the reliable quantification of environmental change. This new extension of EMSA into impact assessment provides a standardised way to survey an area and identify ecological values at risk from proposed developments. They are supported by a toolset for collecting and delivering data to the Australian Government's Biodiversity Data Repository (BDR). This enables data to be used more widely for a range of management, policy and research outcomes.

We intend these protocols to be widely accessible, with minimal assumed knowledge, and to use methods that NRM practitioners and ecologists can easily adopt. We look forward to continuously improving these protocols, extending their use, and supporting other organisations developing similar survey protocols for methods and techniques not currently covered by EMSA.

We know that the data collected and supported by EMSA will enable analyses in novel ways and at previously impossible scales. We thank you for joining us on that journey and look forward to working with you to implement the EMSA system to benefit all Australians.

We welcome you to provide feedback to tern@adelaide.edu.au

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1 Introduction

This document, a *Template and Guidelines for Developing Survey Protocols: Creating monitoring standards compatible with the Ecological Monitoring System Australia (EMSA)*, guides users to develop field survey protocols similar to those created by the Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network. The intended audience of this document are ecologists, environmental practitioners, and experts charged with documenting ecological field methodologies in a standardised, repeatable, and scientifically robust format.

This document should be read in conjunction with:

- The 20+ EMSA modules are readily available on the EMSA website (emsa.tern.org.au), and associated user guides, video tutorials, and supporting documents. We do not provide a specific example here, as we recommend that the user find an existing protocol with a similar purpose to the one they are creating. For example, it would be more useful to use one of the plot-based modules as a guide if your module is plot-based.
- *Survey Guidelines for Monitoring Threatened Species: Towards monitoring standards compatible with the Ecological Monitoring System Australia (TERN 2025)*, which sets out key recommendations for monitoring threatened species populations, species-specific recommendations that identify best-practice methods for a select group of priority threatened species, and general information that can be applied to monitoring all species, regardless of conservation status.

Together, the EMSA modules, the *Survey Guidelines for Monitoring Threatened Species*, and this document aim to improve our knowledge of natural ecosystems, ecological communities, and threatened species by enhancing the accessibility and sharing of high-quality, robust scientific data. By developing best-practice field survey guidelines and recommendations, practitioners will be better equipped to understand the rationale for conducting standardised, repeatable surveys, their implementation, and typical ways to analyse the data collected.

By identifying the monitoring methods typically implemented by practitioners, documenting and assessing the techniques known to work, and identifying opportunities to standardise the methods, we can move towards ensuring all monitoring is ecosystem-appropriate, species-appropriate, comparable between practitioners and populations, and repeatable over time. Further, together with consistent terminology, guidelines, instructions, and data collection, we can refine efforts and resources to measure and share information. Data collected using robust, standardised methods will improve our knowledge of the ecological values of project areas, the presence and importance of areas to threatened species, and enable the impacts of potential disturbances to be assessed rigorously. The extension of EMSA to include a suite of protocols specifically designed to gather ecological data to inform impact assessment is essential to understanding the impact of development.

1.1 Key terminology

It is important to highlight key terms used in EMSA. Whilst 'module' and 'protocols' are often used interchangeably, they refer to different levels of information.

A '**module**' is typically a topic of interest or a high-level method.

For example, the existing EMSA modules include:

- Plot Layout and Selection
- Plot Description
- Photopoints

- Vegetation Mapping
- Floristics
- Plant Tissue Vouchering
- Cover
- Basal Area
- Coarse Woody Debris
- Fire Severity
- Recruitment
- Condition
- Soils
- Signs-based Fauna Surveys
- Fauna Ground Counts
- Vertebrate Fauna
- Invertebrate Fauna.

Appendix 1 describes each of the existing EMSA modules.

'**Protocols**' are typically focused on a specific field method or technique, but can also be a level of survey intensity. For example, the Basal Area Module (which captures the basal area of standing shrubs and trees within a survey area) offers two protocols. The first is the *Basal wedge protocol*, in which a surveyor uses a handheld device (a basal wedge) to measure and record the estimated diameter at breast height of standing trees. Whilst the *DBH protocol* requires the surveyor to use a tape measure to record actual measurements. This is just one example where there are different ways (often with different accuracy levels) of collecting the same type of data.

2 Module template

2.1 Contents of a module

Each EMSA module follows the same format, with its contents following the same 'recipe'. Table 1 outlines the contents of a basic module. The example given only has one protocol. More complex modules may have multiple protocols, in which case section 3 is repeated for each protocol (e.g., sections 4, 5, and 6), and subsequent sections are numbered after them. Some modules offer multiple protocols because each protocol offers a different survey method. For example, the Vertebrate Fauna module has separate modules for bird surveys, active and passive search protocols, and acoustic and ultrasonic records. Other modules have multiple protocols, each offering somewhat different data collection intensities. For example, the Cover Module offers the option of choosing an *Enhanced protocol*, with 10 transects for a total of 1010 points per plot to be surveyed, whilst the *Standard protocol* has just 4 transects for a total of 404 points per plot to be surveyed. Each are essential techniques in particular circumstances, depending on the intent of the monitoring activity.

Table 1. Recommended contents of a module

1	Module overview	
	1.1	Available protocols
	1.2	Relationships to other modules
		1.2.1 Mandatory related modules
		1.2.2 Optional complementary related modules
2	Introduction and background	
	2.1	Key definitions and terminology
	2.1	Rationale
3	Protocol name using descriptive words specific to the method	
	3.1	Field collection
		3.1.1 Prerequisites
		3.1.2 Time requirements
		3.1.3 Personnel requirements
		3.1.4 Equipment
		3.1.5 Instructions and procedures
		3.1.6 Additional guidelines
	3.2	Post-field survey tasks
		3.2.1 Sample curation
4	Data submission	
5	Data use and reason for collection	
	5.1	Data use to date
	5.2	Future use of the data
6	References	
7	Appendices	

2.1.1 Module overview

Available protocols

Each module starts with the **Module overview section**. It is placed at the start to provide the reader with an overview of the module and the protocols it contains.

In this section:

- List, using dot-points, the protocols that the module contains.

Relationships to other modules

In the **Relationships to other modules** section, mention both mandatory related modules and optional complementary modules.

In this section:

- List any mandatory related modules that must be completed prior. For example, if the protocol is conducted within a survey plot, the *Plot Selection and Layout Module* must typically be undertaken first.
- List any complementary modules that may work well with this module. For example, when undertaking the *Floristics Module*, the *Leaf Tissue Sampling Module* can efficiently be conducted at the same time. Similarly, when conducting the *Cover Module*, the *Fire Severity Module* can also be undertaken at the same time, with only a few extra data fields recorded during the surveys.
- If the module does not require any other modules to be completed first, state that it is not dependent on any other modules.

2.1.2 Introduction and background

The **Introduction and background** section is typically a short literature review, and provides the justification for why the methods of the module were selected over other methods.

In this section:

- State alternative methods that are similar, or perhaps more typically used, and highlight why those methods were not selected.
- Highlight the benefits of the selected methods over the alternative methods. This can be for various reasons, including a better ability to standardise the chosen method, that the method detailed is more sensitive to ecological change, quicker time and effort requirements, suitability for a broad range of ecosystems, and the use of readily available instruments over difficult-to-obtain equipment.
- Provide references to relevant reports, instruction manuals, and scientific publications.

Key definitions and terminology

The **Definitions and terminology** section is essential for clarifying the meanings of key terms used in the module. The section is also necessary as the terms used here often link to the database ontologies. Where possible, the easiest route is to adopt terms and definitions from the existing EMSA modules, as they are already defined in the Australian Biodiversity Information Standard (ABIS). ABIS is a data standard that specifies how information about biodiversity is to be represented for exchange and use in Australia. The ABIS standard is available online at the [ABIS website](#). ABIS is centred on TERN ontology, primarily because the DCCEEW Biodiversity Data Repository (BDR) adopted the TERN Ontology as its base. Consequently, due to the collaboration between TERN and DCCEEW in developing EMSA for delivery to the BDR, EMSA has made a significant contribution to the development of ABIS.

In this section:

- List key terms that are important to the module and provide a definition that gives clarity about what the term means.
- List key acronyms used in the module.

- List key measures and environmental attributes being measured in the module if there is potential for them to be misunderstood.
- Where possible, always use existing terms and definitions, especially those already defined in EMSA or ABIS.

Rationale

The purpose of the **Rationale** section is to explain the value of the data being collected in the module. It would typically explain why the information collected is important to assess change and how that can be used to inform research, management and policy.

2.1.3 Protocol section

Give each protocol a descriptive name, either using keywords to describe the method itself or the data intensity. If multiple protocols are similar and only differ by data intensity, call the least data-intensive version the Standard, and the more data-dense version the Enhanced protocol.

Repeat this section for each protocol in the module.

Field collection

The **Field collection** section provides the specifics of the protocol, including the prerequisites, time requirements, personnel requirements, required equipment, instructions, and any additional guidelines. Do not introduce background information in this section (that is provided in the **rationale section**), but rather keep it focused on the vital information that enables the protocol to be repeated without leaving the surveyor distracted by additional references to literature or other options. For clarity, this section does not provide any context, description or references.

Prerequisites

In the **Prerequisites** section:

- List any key steps that must be taken before arriving in the field to conduct the protocol. This could include modules that need to be completed first, for example, for plot-based protocols, the **Plot Selection and Layout Module** should be completed first. For other protocols, equipment, or materials, preparation may be required before arriving in the field.

Time requirements

In the *Time requirements* section:

- Indicate the estimated time required to undertake the protocol, and specify what effects this time assessment has, i.e. the complexity of the vegetation, the number of surveyors assisting. Often, it's helpful to provide a range where the longer estimates are for new surveyors in complex situations and shorter estimates are for experienced surveyors in simpler situations.
- Specify the time estimate for each key component of the protocol: indicate how much time to allow for preparing the site for the survey (e.g., laying out tape measures or installing equipment), as well as the time to actually conduct the survey and pack up the equipment afterwards.

Personnel requirements

In the **Personnel requirements** section:

- List the skills and experience required to undertake the protocols. Most EMSA modules assume some basic ecological survey experience and the ability to follow instructions. If more technical skills are needed, be sure to clearly specify what is expected, as this may prompt consideration of alternative protocols.

- List the number of surveyors needed to conduct the protocol. If some tasks require two or more people, make sure this is clearly specified.
- It may also be appropriate to highlight to the reader any scientific permits or wildlife ethics approvals required to undertake the protocol. It is the survey coordinator's responsibility to obtain the necessary permits and approvals and this should also be made clear in the protocol.

Equipment

In the **Equipment** section:

- List the equipment necessary to conduct the protocols. Where necessary, be specific—for example, list the length of the tape measure required and the sizes of the traps.
- For technical equipment, be specific and recommend makes, models, minimum firmware versions, and memory card read/write speed requirements.
- For equipment that needs to be constructed, provide a separate step-by-step instruction sheet and consider creating a video as well.
- Remember to list a tablet or mobile device for field data collection and the apps to install before arriving in the field.
- List all consumable and general items also required to undertake the protocol, such as flagging tape, chalk, and marking paint.

Instructions and procedures

The **Instructions and procedures** section is the key component of the protocol. It provides the step-by-step instructions for the surveyors to survey in a standardised, repeatable manner.

In this section:

- Create subheadings for each key section of the protocol, and ideally define any pre-survey planning tasks, site preparation tasks (such as transect set-up), and the section for actually conducting the survey steps where observations are made.
- Break down each step of the procedure, and start at the beginning, from when the surveyor arrives at the survey location. Usually, each step is numbered.
- Keep each step short and straight to the point. Break down points into sub-points when it helps.
- When a step allows multiple ways of being conducted, pick a way and specify it, rather than giving the surveyor multiple options and leaving them to wonder which to choose. For example, it often does not matter whether something is measured top-down or bottom-up; for simplicity, pick one and stick with it. Similarly, do not be afraid to be super clear about a step—for example, holding the pole with your left hand and positioning your body so that your right eye can see through the eye slot.
- Cover every step of the procedure until the measure is recorded adequately.
- Remember, when writing instructions and procedures to match an app, datasheet or data form workflow, follow in a logical sequence that matches.

Additional guidelines

The **Additional guidelines** section allows the survey to know of any hints, tips, and recommendations for conducting the survey. This section, however, is not where key steps are detailed—all key steps must be in the **Instructions and procedures** section.

The *Additional guidelines* section is typically read by surveyors the first time they prepare or conduct the survey, but after gaining some experience, it may be skipped once the surveyor is familiar with the content.

In this section:

- Identify how to separate tasks for individual surveyors and assistants to ensure efficient workflows.
- Identify any rules and decisions that may need to be made when conducting the protocols. For example, in the Basal Area Module, the *Additional guidelines* section includes rules on how to measure 'problem trees' that do not conform to typical trunk girths to allow for straightforward measurements. A series of illustrations is also provided to help the surveyor understand the rules to apply.

2.1.4 Post-field survey tasks

Sample curation

The Post-field survey tasks section may only be appropriate to include for some protocols.

In this section:

- List any instructions needed to curate any samples collected. For example, for flora samples taken, press each sample in a plant press, change the paper regularly until dry, or use other methods to dry the samples until they are dry and stable to avoid them going mouldy.

2.1.5 Data submission

The *Data submission* section is critical to ensuring that observations made during the survey are secured and that no survey results are lost. Most EMSA modules collect all data in the field directly using the Monitor app. Once the surveyor reconnects to the internet, the data is pushed to a holding repository.

In this section:

- Identify steps the surveyor needs to take in order to secure the data captured in the field. This may include manually saving files to secure drives and uploading files to databases.
- List any instructions to download photographs taken in the field, either with cameras, the data collection tablet, or camera traps.
- List any instructions to download digital files, such as those collected by acoustic recorders or camera traps, and next steps on what to do with the files to enable analysis.

2.1.6 Data use and reason for collection

Data use to date

Whilst similar to the **Rationale** provided earlier in the module, the **Data use to date section**, highlights to the reader examples of how the data can be used. It can provide insights into how the data collected can be analysed.

Future use of the data

The **Future use of the data** section, extends the **Data use to date** section, and identifies additional uses. Example uses may include providing ground-truthed data validation to support more innovative technologies as they emerge and become more widespread. Additionally, some uses may only be possible once extensive datasets are developed and made readily accessible. For impact assessment purposes, the role of the data collected for strategic assessments cannot be underestimated.

2.1.7 References

As with all documents, the **References** section lists all references cited in the module. Be sure to include complete references for all citations and, where possible, digital object identifiers (DOIs). This section is often used to highlight methods used/adapted in the protocols.

2.1.8 Appendices

In the *Appendices* section, include any additional information that will assist the surveyors in completing the protocols, but is too cumbersome to include in the main text of the document.

In this section:

- Include tables listing all relevant data fields for the module. For example, include all drop-down lists that would appear in an app, as well as the tick-box category options that would appear on a datasheet or data form.
- Include any instructions for constructing equipment.
- Include any templates for labels to attach to samples collected.

3 Module refinement

Modules are able to be updated, although it's essential to clearly version them when doing so. Care must be taken to ensure that edits and additions either do not affect the standard or that proper version control is implemented. It is vital that version control maintains a single source of truth.

Edits that improve readability, provide further information in the *Introduction and background*, and *Data use and reason for collection* sections, or improve the Data submission processes, can still impact how the standard is interpreted. It's essential that the core collected information is not changed in any way.

TERN is happy to provide advice when you're creating protocols using this template..

4 Appendices

Appendix 1. Description of the Ecological Monitoring System of Australia (EMSA) modules

EMSA Manuals and sample datasheets are available from the [EMSA website](#). The EMSA app, Monitor, supports in-field electronic data collection of these modules.

Module name	Module description
Basal area	Records basal area within plots where there is a dominant growth form of trees, shrubs and/or mallee greater than 2 m in height. An enhanced diameter at breast height (DBH), standard DBH or basal wedge protocol may be used. Data captured includes the species name, tree details, number of trees that are wider than the aperture of the basal area factor etc.
Camera trapping	Covers three camera trapping protocols (deployment, re-equipping and retrieval). Camera traps can be deployed at one or more features of interest, or in an array (i.e., grid or transect) or a fauna plot. Data captured includes survey type, camera trap make, model and settings, camera trap location and orientation, focal point, target species if applicable, bait station details, deployment period etc.
Coarse woody debris	This module covers procedures and guidelines to record coarse woody debris (CWD) length, diameter and decay class in the plot, using either a standard or enhanced protocol. Data captured includes plot size, CWD measurements and decay class.
Condition	Records biodiversity condition of the plot using a combination of point and plot-based methods. Data is collected on plant age class structure, plant health and size, litter depth, coarse woody debris and recruitment. Data from other modules also provide important measures for overall assessment of condition. Data captured includes a tree survey (diameter at breast height, species name, growth stage etc.), leaf litter depth, grazing damage etc.
Cover	Records vegetation and substrate cover within the plot using the point-intercept method with either a standard or enhanced protocol. Data captured includes substrate type, species occurrence and abundance, growth form, and height.
Fauna aerial surveys	Record fauna observations during an aerial survey from a manned aircraft. Data captured includes aircraft and model, observers, altitude, transect length, species, number, distance observed etc.
Fauna ground counts	Direct counts of fauna using transects or vantage point protocols. The module is designed for monitoring pest fauna species, but can be used on all fauna species. It may be combined with other fauna monitoring modules to estimate abundance and assess impacts of fauna species. Data captured includes date, time, location and count of observed fauna species, distance from the observer and optional details such as age class.
Fire severity	Records fire severity within the plot by recording cover and height of fire severity attributes from the ground to the canopy (at 404 point-intercepts along four 100 m transects within the plot), and trunk char height at four locations within the plot. Data captured includes fire ignition date, substrate, vascular plant information, resprouting etc.
Floristics	Record flora species composition in the plot using either a standard or enhanced protocol. Vouchers of some or all species in the plot must be collected and sent to a state or territory herbarium. All vouchers are barcoded and linked to the species ID in the Monitor app. Data captured includes field name, growth forms and vouchers (physical and photo).
Herbivory and physical damage	Record herbivory and physical damage from vertebrate fauna using up to 3 protocols (within-plot belt transect, off-plot belt transect, active plot search). The module is designed for monitoring pest fauna species, but can be used on all fauna species. It may be combined with other fauna monitoring modules to estimate abundance and assess impacts of fauna species. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: presence or absence of damage type, count of damage, age of the damage etc.
Invertebrate fauna	This module includes 5 field sampling protocols for terrestrial invertebrates (active search, wet pitfall trapping, rapid ground trapping, pan trapping and malaise trapping) and a post-field sample curation protocol. Invertebrates are collected and preserved to future-proof data and enable future identification. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: search time, weather, collection apparatus, trap location, photos, vouchers etc.
Opportune	Records opportune observations of flora (vascular and non-vascular) and fauna (vertebrate and invertebrate). Opportune observations are unplanned (no defined survey effort) and made while undertaking other activities, at any stage of a project. Observations often occur while travelling between plots and while undertaking other modules. Data collected includes date, time, location, species ID, number of individuals location, habitat, optional vouchers etc.

Pest fauna control activities	Includes pest fauna removal activities such as shooting, baiting, trapping and mustering. This module records the number of target animals removed or bait taken to monitor pest fauna abundance. Data captured includes target species, control method, survey effort, weather conditions etc.
Photopoints	Establishes 3 photopoints around the plot's centre, using one of three protocols (DSLR camera panorama, compact camera panorama, device camera panorama). Data collected includes plot ID and 360 degree panoramas from three points around the plot centre.
Plant tissue vouchering	Procedures and guidelines for collecting, drying and storing plant tissue vouchers within a plot using either a standard or enhanced protocol. All samples collected are barcoded, linking the voucher to the species. Data captured includes species field name, barcode ID and growth forms.
Plot Description	Describe the landform, land surface and vegetation of a plot using either a standard or enhanced protocol. Information recorded includes landform, slope and aspect, lithology, disturbance, fire history and vegetation type. Data collected includes slope, aspect, lithology, growth stage, fire history, site disturbance etc.
Plot selection and layout	This module includes procedures and guidelines for a desktop assessment of the project area and proposed plot locations, selection of plot locations in the field and marking out the plots. Plot types include the core monitoring plot and an optional paired fauna plot (both 100 x 100 m; 1 ha). Plot selection is a preliminary requirement for most modules. Data collected includes the plot layout and type.
Recruitment	This module includes 2 protocols for recording age class structure and survivorship of vegetation within the plot. Data captured includes actual count of individuals, life stage (seedling, flowering, fruiting, seeding, senescent etc.) and can also include tagging of individuals for ongoing monitoring of survivorship.
Sign-based fauna surveys	Record fauna signs in the project area using up to 5 protocols (within-plot belt transect, off-plot belt transect, plot sign search, vehicle tracks and track stations). The module is designed for monitoring pest fauna species, but can be used on all fauna species. It may be combined with other fauna monitoring modules to estimate abundance and assess impacts of fauna species. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: sign presence or absence, sign details, photos etc.
Soils	This module includes 4 soil protocols: soil sub-pit and metagenomics (Standard or enhanced protocol), sample pit, site observation and pit characterisation and bulk density. Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: sample location and photos, soil horizon detail, soil classification etc.
Targeted surveys	Collections metadata of surveys conducted recording an overview of the monitoring type, the scale of the monitoring, the landscapes, target species/communities, records the type of data the monitoring captured, identified data custodian contact details, and where the data is accessible from.
Vegetation mapping	Classify vegetation at precise points across the project area. Collect structural and floristic data within homogeneous vegetation that is representative of vegetation associations. Data collected includes homogeneity measure, photo, percentage cover, growth stage, fire history, disturbance etc.
Vertebrate fauna	Survey for vertebrate fauna species present within the plot using up to 5 survey protocols: trapping survey set-up and closure (standard or enhanced protocol), identify, measure and release, bird survey, active and passive search, and acoustic and ultrasonic recordings. Surveys can be completed either as trapping or non-trapping surveys. Any vouchering must be conducted under guidance from the state/territory jurisdictional museum (module does not include protocols for vouchering). Depending on protocols completed, data captured can include: trap specifications, trap success rate, species observed and population demographics, recapture of individuals, call files etc.